

Organophosphorus Compounds. XII. The Reaction of Alkyl Phosphites and Diphenylphosphinodithioic Acid with 2N-Phenyl- α , β -Naphtho-1, 2, 3,-Triazolequinone

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The reaction of dimethyl-, diethyl-, and diisopropyl phosphite with 2N-phenyl- α , β -naphtho-1,2,3-triazolequinone (II), in benzene solution, leads to the formation of the corresponding *o*-quinolmonophosphates IIIa-c. In petroleum ether, quinone II gives with diisopropyl phosphite a 1 : 1 adduct believed to have a structure similar to IV or the possible tautomeric form V.

Trimethyl-, triethyl-, and/or triisopropyl phosphite react with quinone II to give 1 : 1 adducts formulated as VIIIa-c, respectively. Diphenylphosphinodithioic acid, thiophenol as well as *p*-chlorothiophenol add to the triazole quinone (II) in a molar ratio to give compounds having structure IX.

Spectroscopic data are in favour of the assigned structures.

In continuation of the work reported earlier from this Laboratory on the behaviour of heterocyclic nitrogen *o*-quinones, e.g., 1,2-benzophenazine-3,4-quinone (I) towards alkyl phosphites¹, the action of di-, and trialkyl phosphites on 2N-phenyl- α -, β -naphtho-1,2,3-triazolequinone (II) has now been investigated.

When the orange quinone II was allowed to react with dimethyl-, diethyl-, or diisopropyl phosphite, in hot benzene, colourless 1 : 1 adducts (IIIa-c) were obtained.

The reaction of dialkyl phosphites with the triazole quinone (II) has been found to be catalyzed by direct sunlight. This reaction is regarded as radical chain process². It seems likely that the photochemical effect is due to the excitation of quinone II to its diradicals (or triplet state). The photo-dissociation, $(\text{RO})_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H} \rightarrow (\text{RO})_2\text{P}(\text{O})\cdot + \text{H}\cdot$, cannot provide the required radicals³.

The similarity of formation of the adducts IIIa-c suggests that they are of analogous constitution. In favour of the proposed structure, taking IIIc as an example, are the following : (i) Elemental analysis agrees with the formula $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_3\text{O}_5\text{P}$. (ii) The IR spectrum of IIIc, in KBr, shows a broad absorption band around 3400 cm^{-1} ($-\text{OH}$). There is practically no absorption in the carbonyl region, ($1780-1610\text{ cm}^{-1}$), observed with quinone II near 1667 cm^{-1} . The spectrum also shows absorptions at 1280 cm^{-1} ($\text{---}\overset{\diagup}{\text{P}}=\text{O}$, free)⁴; at 1230 cm^{-1} ($\text{---}\overset{\diagup}{\text{P}}\rightarrow\text{O}$, hydrogen bonded)⁴ and at 1010 cm^{-1} which appears to be of the P-O-C (isopropyl)⁴. (iii) The adduct IIIc is freely soluble in 5% aqueous sodium hydroxide

(II) to yield colourless 1:1 adducts believed to have structure similar to VII or the corresponding cyclic unsaturated pentaoxyphosphorane structures (VIIIa-c).

Since an alkyl group translocation is known⁹ to occur in the reaction of trialkyl phosphites with *p*-quinones, the isomeric phosphate ester structure (III, R = R' = alkyl) also should be considered. The non-identity of the quinone-trimethyl phosphite adduct with compound IIIId, obtained by the action of diazomethane on IIIa, suggests that both compounds are not of analogous constitution. The phosphate ester structure (III, R = R' = alkyl), seems therefore not to be consistent with that assigned for the reaction products of trialkyl phosphites with quinone II. The IR spectrum of compound VIIIc, taken as an example, in KBr, shows no absorption bands in the 1350–1250 cm⁻¹ region, characteristic for the phosphoryl absorption⁴, and the band at 1020 cm⁻¹ appears to be of the P–O–C (isopropyl) absorption frequency⁴. The NMR spectrum of the adduct VIIIc, in CDCl₃, is compatible with the oxyphosphorane structure (VIII) and possibly favours it over the open dipolar structure (VII). The spectrum shows the presence of 18 protons as a doublet centered at τ 8.73 resulting from the isopropyloxy groups. A multiplet is visible for the three methine protons centered at τ 4.9. All the aromatic protons fall in the region τ 2.08–2.90. The integral is defined as a proton ratio value of 9.

Compounds VIIIa-c are insoluble in 5% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution and give no colour reaction with alcoholic ferric chloride. Upon treatment with anhydrous hydrogen chloride in dry ether solution, compound VIIIa gave the corresponding *o*-quinolmonophosphate (IIIa).

It is of interest to report here that diphenylphosphinodithioic acid [(C₆H₅)₂P(S)SH], a thiol phosphoric acid, thiophenol as well as *p*-chlorothiophenol add to the triazolequinone (II) in a molar ratio to give colourless compounds formulated as IXa-c, respectively*. Spectroscopic and chemical evidences are also in favour of the assigned structure. The UV spectrum of the adduct IXa, in ethanol, resembles that of quinone II. No marked

* Cf. the marked difference in the behaviour of *o*-quinones and α -dicarbonyl compounds towards aromatic thiols (1,10,11).

shifts have been observed in the absorptions around $230\text{ m}\mu$, $265\text{ m}\mu$ and $300\text{ m}\mu$ regions, respectively. The IR spectrum of IXa, in KBr, reveals the presence of absorption bands around 3200 cm^{-1} ($-\text{OH}$, hydrogen bonded); 1710 cm^{-1} ($-\overset{\text{O}}{\text{C}}=\text{O}$). Adducts IXa-c are insoluble in 5% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution, exhibit no colour reaction with alcoholic ferric chloride and regenerate the starting quinone (II) when treated with aqueous sodium hydroxide solution⁶ or upon heating above their melting points.

EXPERIMENTAL

All melting points are uncorrected. The benzene (thiophene-free) and ether (peroxide-free) used, were dried over metallic sodium. Dialkyl phosphites were freshly prepared and the trialkyl phosphites were purified by treatment with sodium followed by fractional distillation. Petroleum ether had b.p. 40° - 60° .

The IR spectra were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer 137 Spectrophotometer; the NMR spectrum with a Varian A-60 machine and the UV spectra with a Carl-Zeiss PMQ II Spectrophotometer in spectroscopic ethanol.

Reaction of Dimethyl Phosphite with 2N-phenyl- α , β -naphtho-1,2,3-triazolequinone (II) in Benzene: A mixture of the orange quinone II¹² (0.27 g; 0.001 mole), dimethyl phosphite¹³ (0.11 g; 0.001 mole) and dry benzene (30 ml) was boiled under reflux for 6 hr, whereby the colour of the solution fades considerably. The benzene solution was concentrated to half its original volume and petroleum ether then added. The mixture was left to cool in the ice-chest and the solid material, so obtained, was filtered off, washed with petroleum ether and then crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether to give IIIa as colourless crystals, m.p. 110 - 112° (dec.) (0.23 g; 60% yield). (Found: C, 55.49; H, 5.09; N, 10.67; P, 8.39. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_3\text{O}_5\text{P}$ requires: C, 55.51; H, 5.18; N, 10.70; P, 8.48%).

Similarly, compounds IIIb and IIIc were obtained by the reaction of quinone II with diethyl-,¹⁴ and diisopropyl phosphite¹³, respectively.

Compound IIIb was obtained as colourless crystals from benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 123° - 125° (dec.) (70% yield). (Found: C, 58.21; H, 4.85; N, 10.09; P, 7.39. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_3\text{O}_5\text{P}$ requires: C, 58.11; H, 4.87; N, 10.16; P, 7.49%).

Compound IIIc was crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether in colourless crystals, m.p. 130° - 132° (dec.) (75% yield). (Found: C, 59.28; H, 6.16; N, 10.01; P, 6.99. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_3\text{O}_5\text{P}$ requires: C, 59.31; H, 6.34; N, 9.43; P, 6.95%).

Compounds IIIa-c are soluble in 5% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution and give a green colour reaction with alcoholic ferric chloride solution.

Photochemical Reaction between Quinone II and Diisopropyl Phosphite: Quinone II (0.27 g) and freshly distilled diisopropyl phosphite (0.17 g), in dry benzene (50 ml) were exposed to sunlight for 48 hrs. (September). The benzene solution was then concentrated to half its original volume and diluted with an equivalent amount of petroleum ether. The crystals that separated after cooling were collected, crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether and proved to be identical with IIIc (m.p. and mixed m.p.) (55% yield).

Action of Diazomethane on IIIa : To a suspension of IIIa (0.3 g) in dry ether (20 ml) was added an ethereal solution of diazomethane (from 3 g. N-nitrosomethylurea) with occasional shaking and the reaction mixture then left at 5° for 24 hr. Ether was distilled off and the residue, that left, was crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether to give IIIId as colourless crystals, m.p. 62°–64° (60% yield). (Found : C, 57.24; H, 4.53; N, 10.50; P, 7.68. $C_{19}H_{18}N_3O_5P$ requires : C, 57.14; H, 4.54; N, 10.52; P, 7.68%).

Similarly, compound IIIe was obtained by the action of ethereal diazomethane on IIIc.

Compound IIIe was crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether as yellow crystals, m.p. 75°–77° (65% yield). (Found : C, 60.71; H, 5.78; N, 9.19; P, 6.57. $C_{23}H_{26}N_3O_5P$ requires : C, 60.65; H, 5.75; N, 9.22; P, 6.80%).

Compounds IIIId and IIIe are insoluble in 5% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution and give no colour with alcoholic ferric chloride solution.

Acid Hydrolysis of IIIa : To a solution of compound IIIa (0.2 g) in glacial acetic acid (15 ml) was added concentrated hydrochloric acid (3 ml, sp. gr. 1.18). The reaction mixture was boiled under reflux for 5 hr. After cooling, the mixture was poured onto ice-cooled water, neutralized with sodium bicarbonate solution (10%). The orange residue that deposited was collected, washed with water, dried and then crystallized from acetic acid and proved to be 2N-phenyl- α,β -naphtho-1,2,3-triazolequinone (II) (m.p. and mixed m.p.).

Similarly, quinone II was regenerated upon hydrolysis of IIIb and IIIc, respectively, with acetic-hydrochloric acid mixture.

Alkali Hydrolysis of IIIa : A mixture of compound IIIa (0.2 g) and 10% aqueous alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution (30 ml, 1 : 1) was refluxed for 3 hr. The alcoholic solution was concentrated to half its original volume, left to cool and then neutralized with dilute hydrochloric acid (10%). The orange substance that separated out was collected, washed with water, dried, crystallized from acetic acid and proved to be quinone II (m.p. and mixed m.p.).

Reaction of 2N-Phenyl- α,β -naphtho-1,2,3-triazolequinone (II) with Dimethyl Phosphite in Petroleum Ether : A mixture of quinone II (0.27 g; 0.001 mole), freshly distilled dimethyl phosphite (0.11 g; 0.001 mole) and petroleum ether (30 ml); was refluxed on the steam bath for 6 hr. After cooling, the solid material that separated was filtered off, washed with petroleum ether and finally crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether to give colourless crystals proved to be IIIa, (m.p. and mixed m.p.) (ca. 0.2 g; 50% yield).

Compound IIIb has also been obtained (m.p. and mixed m.p.) when quinone II was allowed to react with diethyl phosphite under similar conditions.

Reaction of Diisopropyl Phosphite with 2N-Phenyl- α,β -naphtho-1,2,3-triazolequinone (II) in Petroleum Ether : A mixture of quinone II (0.27 g; 0.001 mole), freshly distilled diisopropyl phosphite (0.17 g; 0.001 mole) and petroleum ether (30 ml) was refluxed on the steam bath for 6 hr. After cooling, the solid material that separated was filtered off, washed with

petroleum ether and finally crystallized from benzene to give adduct "A" as colourless crystals, m.p. 173°–175° (dec.) (0.35 g; 80% yield). (Found : C, 59.28; H, 6.33; N, 9.42; P, 6.98. $C_{22}H_{24}N_3O_5P$ requires : C, 59.31; H, 6.34; N, 9.42; P, 6.95%).

When dissolved in ethanol and kept at room temperature for 24 hr or heated in benzene solution for 6 hr, adduct "A" was readily converted, almost quantitatively, to the corresponding *o*-quinolmonophosphate (IIIc) (m.p. and mixed m.p.).

Action of Trimethyl Phosphite on 2N-Phenyl- α,β -naphtho-1,2,3-triazolequinone (II) : A mixture of quinone II (0.27 g; 0.001 mole), dry benzene (20 ml) and trimethyl phosphite¹⁵ (0.12 g; 0.001 mole) was refluxed for 8 hr. After removal of the volatile materials under reduced pressure, the oily residue, left behind, was triturated for several times with petroleum ether. The colourless crystals, thus formed, were collected, washed with petroleum ether, dried and crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether to give VIIIA as colourless crystals, m.p. 135°–137° (0.31 g; 65% yield). (Found : C, 56.54; H, 5.45; N, 10.47; P, 7.69. $C_{19}H_{18}N_3O_5P$ requires : C, 56.57; H, 5.49; N, 10.41; P, 7.67%).

In a similar manner, the following compounds were obtained by the action of triethyl and triisopropyl phosphite¹⁶ on quinone II.

The colourless quinone-triethyl phosphite adduct (VIIIB), m.p. 127°–129° (80% yield), from chloroform-petroleum ether. (Found : C, 59.96; H, 5.54; N, 9.49; P, 6.98. $C_{22}H_{24}N_3O_5P$ requires : C, 59.86; H, 5.48; N, 9.52; P, 7.02%).

The colourless quinone-triisopropyl phosphite adduct (VIIIC), m.p. 137°–139° (80% yield), from benzene-petroleum ether. (Found : C, 61.57; H, 7.01; N, 8.59; P, 6.34. $C_{25}H_{30}N_3O_5P$ requires : C, 61.58; H, 7.03; N, 8.62; P, 6.35%).

Compounds VIIIA–c are insoluble in 5% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution and give no colour reaction with alcoholic ferric chloride solution.

Action of Dry Hydrogen Chloride on VIIIA : A stream of dry hydrogen chloride gas was passed into a solution of compound VIIIA (0.3 g) in dry ether (20 ml) for 2 hr. Ether was evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue left behind was dissolved in benzene, treated with petroleum ether and then left to cool in the ice-chest. The colourless crystals that separated were filtered, crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether and proved to be IIIa (m.p. and mixed m.p.).

Action of Diphenylphosphinodithioic Acid on Quinone II : To a solution of quinone II (0.27 g; 0.001 mole) in dry benzene (20 ml) was added a solution of diphenylphosphinodithioic acid¹⁷ (0.25 g; 0.001 mole) in dry benzene (10 ml). The mixture was boiled under reflux for 2 hr and left to cool. Petroleum ether was added and the precipitated material, so formed, was filtered off, washed with petroleum ether, dried and then crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether to give IXa as colourless crystals, m.p. 138°–140° (0.42 g; 80% yield). (Found : C, 63.49; H, 4.45; N, 7.89; P, 5.94; S, 12.16. $C_{28}H_{20}N_3O_2PS_2$ requires : C, 63.51; H, 4.50; N, 7.99; P, 5.89; S, 12.20%).

Similarly, compounds IXb and IXc were obtained by the reaction of quinone II with thiophenol and *p*-chlorothiophenol, respectively.

Compound IXb was obtained from petroleum ether (b.p. 60°–80°) as colourless crystals, m.p. 180°–182° (65% yield). (Found : C, 68.56; H, 3.94; N, 11.03; S, 8.34. $C_{22}H_{15}N_3O_2S$ requires : C, 68.55; H, 3.92; N, 10.90; S, 8.31%).

Compound IXc was obtained from petroleum ether (b.p. 60°–80°) as colourless crystals, m.p. 178°–180° (70% yield). (Found : C, 65.84; H, 3.60; Cl, 8.50; N, 10.12; S, 7.68. $C_{22}H_{14}ClN_3O_2S$ requires : C, 65.75; H, 3.51; Cl, 8.44; N, 10.00; S, 7.64%).

The quinone-thiol adducts IXa–c are insoluble in 5% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution and give no colour reaction with alcoholic ferric chloride solution.

Alkali Hydrolysis of IXb : A mixture of the adduct IXb (0.2 g), ethanol (10 ml) and aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (10 ml; 10%) was refluxed for 3 hr. The alcoholic solution was concentrated to half its volume, cooled and then neutralized with dilute (10%) hydrochloric acid. The yellow orange material that separated, was collected, dried, crystallized from acetic and proved to be the quinone II (m.p. and mixed m.p.)¹².

Action of Heat on IXb : 0.3 g of the adduct IXb was heated in a cold finger sublimator at 190°–200° (bath temperature) under reduced pressure (2 mm/Hg) for about 15 min. The substance that sublimed was collected, crystallized from acetic acid and proved to be quinone II (m.p. and mixed m.p.) (yield ca. 0.3 g.).

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